

ATTITUDES TOWARDS DISCUSSIONS IN ISLAM

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Annotation. Life sciences in the contemporary world are fertile ground for religion and science contentions. It could be argued that developments in evolutionary biology in the last two centuries contributed much to the rise of New Atheism. On conducting a survey we find that the study of life sciences within the Islamic scientific tradition never inclined towards atheistic thought. A core characteristic of Islamic science was that rigorous scientific research was conducted within a predominantly Islamic intellectual milieu and a 'tawhid' framework. The initial impetus to develop life sciences in the Muslim world came from religious injunctions from the Quran and Sunnah. Many scientists like Muhammad ibn Sirin, Hasan Basri etc pursued a study of the world to understand divine wisdom at work in creation. The necessary starting point of all scientific enquiry in the Islamic world was a recognition of divine unity that is demonstrated best by cosmic unity. Because Islamic science sprang forth from an intellectual tradition rooted in religion and spirituality, the place of symbolism in all literature was inevitable. Understanding this feature of Islamic science is crucial for various reasons like a historical survey of Islamic Science and contemporary efforts in the field of Islam and Science, particularly Evolution.

Keywords: Muhammad ibn Sirin, Hasan Basri, Spirituality, Islamic Science.

If you look at the history of mankind, it is clear that since the beginning of time, there have been exchanges of ideas, debates, debates, debates and debates among people on various topics, and it is very likely that there will be in the future. In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the phrase "controversy" is described as a discussion, argument, which takes place in favor of something, situation or issue. ¹Among existing philosophical concepts and religious views, Islam has its own attitude to the concept of debate.

In the sacred sources of Islam, a number of words can be traced to the controversial controversy. Among them: "miroun" (*مراء*) - to talk or dispute; jadal (*جدال*) - to argue or argue; Ikhtisom (*اختصم*) - phrases such as arguing or talking occur in several places in the Qur'an. Although the above expressions are mainly negative arguments, there are also points that can be understood in positive terms.

From the Shariah point of view, "miroun" means showing oneself openly, humiliating one's opponent, standing above others. The goal is not to establish the truth, but to establish and protect one's "I". Taking into account these points of view, the phrase "miroun" has been criticized in many works from Salafu-s-Salih.

Ibn Abbas: *لا تمار أخاك؛ فإن المراء لا تفهم حكمته، ولا تؤمن غائلته*. Do not argue with your brother in vain, neither wisdom can be understood from useless arguments, nor calamities can be avoided ².

¹ Annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language / under the editorship of Z.M. Ma'rufov. - M: Russian Language Publishing House, 1981. - T.1, p.91

² Muhiddin ibnu-l-Asir Jazari *Jami'u-l-usul fi ahdisu-r-rasul*. - Damascus: Dor ibn Kasir, 2016. - J.2, p.218-219

Abu Zarr says: *المراء من استحقاق حقيقة الإيمان ترك المراء* - Leaving useless arguments is considered as reaching the truth of faith ³.

Abu Dardo says: *كفى بك إثماً أن لا تزال ممرارياً* - As long as you continue to argue in vain, there is enough sin in you ⁴.

Ibn Umar says: *ولن يصيب رجل حقيقة الإيمان حتى يترك المراء، وهو يعلم أنه صادق، ويترك الكذب في المزاحه* - A person will never reach the truth of faith even if he makes useless arguments about himself, or if he does not leave lying as a joke ⁵.

Mu'az ibn Jabal said: " *إذا أحببت أخاً فلا تماره* " **If you love your brother, do not argue with him in vain** ⁶.

Ibn Abi Layoli: *لا تمار أخاك؛ فإنه لا يأتي بخير* - Do not argue with your brother in vain, it will not bring any good - he said ⁷.

Muhammad ibn Idris Shafiiy said: *المراء في العلم يقسي القلوب، ويورث الضغائن* - Useless arguments about knowledge harden the heart and create anger (and hatred) in them ⁸.

Muhammad ibn Sirin said: *من صفة الجاحل: الجدال، و المراء، والمغالبة* - The characteristics of the ignorant are: futile arguing, seeking superiority and the desire to win (that is, always being right) - he said ⁹.

Hasan Basri says: *ما رأينا فقيهاً يماري* - We have not seen a jurist engaged in useless debate ¹⁰.

Sometimes the phrase "miroun" appears in a positive sense in the Qur'an: *فَلَا تَمَارِ فِيهِمْ إِلَّا مِرَاءً* - **So discuss openly about them only (on the basis of revelation) and do not ask any of them questions about (the Companions of Kahf) (Kahf, 22)** ¹¹.

also be seen that the phrase "al-jadal" (*الجدال*) is used for a useless argument. In this regard, the Qur'an says: *فَمَنْ قَرَضَ فِيهِنَّ الْحَجَّ فَلَا رَفْتٌ وَلَا فُسُوقٌ وَلَا جِدَالٌ فِي الْحَجِّ* - **So, whoever makes Hajj obligatory (intentions to perform Hajj) during Hajj, approaching his wife, sinning, and arguing are not permitted . (Baqarah, 197)** ¹².

In the works of the Salafu-s-Salihes, one can see negative opinions about "jadal". Malik ibn Anas: *كلما جاء رجل أجدل من رجل، تركنا ما نزل به جبريل على محمد عليه السلام لجدل* - Whenever a person who likes to argue came, we would leave behind what came to Gabriel Muhammad, peace be upon him - he said ¹³. Al-Awzai says: *إثا عرد الله بقوم شرأثت الزمهم الجدل، ومنعم العمل* - When Allah wants evil for a people, He makes them wasteful arguments and deprives them of the opportunity to act ¹⁴.

However, it can be seen that the phrase "jidol" appears in the Qur'an in a positive sense: *إذا أراءك* - **They (Nuh's people) said: "O Noah! You argued with us , but you took the argument too far. So, if you are among the truthful, then bring us that**

³ Hannad ibn Sari Kufi Kitabu-z-Zuhd. - Kuwait: Daru-l-khulafa li-l-kitabi-l-islami, 1985. - J.2, p.557

⁴ Abu Dawood Sijjistani. Kitab-z-Zuhd. - Cairo: Daru-l-Mishkot, 1993. - B.259

⁵ Ahmad ibn Hanbal. Az-Zuhd. - Beirut: Doru-l-kutubi-l-ilmiya, 1999. - B.292

⁶ Muhammad ibn Ismail Bukhari. Al-Adabu-l-mufrad. - Al-Jubail (Saudi Arabia): Daru-s-siddiq, 2000. - B.187

⁷ Hannad ibn Sari Kufi Kitabu-z-Zuhd. - Kuwait: Daru-l-khulafa li-l-kitabi-l-islami, 1985. - J.2, p.557

⁸ Muhammad ibn Muflih Maqdisi. Al-Adabu-sh-sharia. - Beirut: Muassasatu-r-risala, 1999. - J.1, p.222

⁹ Abu Bakr Muhammad ibn Husayn Ojuri. Akhlaqu-l-ulama. - Damascus: Doru-l-Kalam, 2001. - B.58

¹⁰ That source. - P.55.

¹¹ Holy Quran: translation and interpretation of meanings / translation and interpretation author: Abdulaziz Mansur. - T: TIU, 2012. - P.296.

¹² That source. - P.31.

¹³ Muhammad ibn Muflih Maqdisi. Al-Adabu-sh-sharia. - V:1. - Beirut: Muassasatu-r-risala, 1999. - P.222

¹⁴ That source. - V:1. - P.222.

thing (torment) that you scared! (Hood, 32) ¹⁵, or: **ادْعُ إِلَى سَبِيلِ رَبِّكَ بِالْحُكْمَةِ وَالْمَوْعِظَةِ الْحَسَنَةِ وَجَادِلْهُمْ** - **بِالَّتِي هِيَ أَحْسَنُ** - (O Muhammad!) **Invite to the path (religion)** of your Lord with wisdom and beautiful advice! **Debate with them in the most beautiful way!** (Nahl, 125) ¹⁶. In addition, it can be seen that the expression "jidol" appears in the Qur'an in the sense of seeking advice: **قَدْ سَمِعَ اللَّهُ قَوْلَ الَّتِي تُجَادِلُكَ فِي زَوْجِهَا وَتَشْتَكِي إِلَى اللَّهِ وَاللَّهُ يَسْمَعُ تَحَاوُرَكُمَا إِنَّ اللَّهَ سَمِيعٌ بَصِيرٌ** **You say the word of a woman who was with you to her husband and complaining to God. Allah hears your conversation. Indeed, Allah is All-Hearing and All-Seeing (Mujodala, 1)** ¹⁷.

Among the expressions used in the Qur'an for useless arguments, we can also mention the word "Ikhtisam": **قَالَ قَرِينُهُ رَبَّنَا مَا أَطَعَيْتُهُ وَلَكِنْ كَانَ فِي ضَلَالٍ بَعِيدٍ* قَالَ لَا تَخْتَصِمُوا لَدَيَّ وَقَدْ قَدَّمْتُ إِلَيْكُمْ بِالْوَعِيدِ** - **His neighbor (Satan):** "Lord, I tied him up no , but he himself was far astray (from the right path)," **he says. (Allah) says: " Do not argue before me !" I have warned you before** (Qaf, 27-28) ¹⁸.

According to the results of the given information, it does not mean that there is no way to debate in Islam. The reason is that there is a scientific debate and several expressions are mainly used in it. In particular, "al-munaqasa" (**المناقشة**) is a discussion (discussion), in which the two sides exchange their arguments, each of them analyzes and compares their personal points of view. The goal is to find out the truth. Such debates take place in the form of a free conversation with a narrow circle of etiquette.

Also "al-munozara" (**مناظرة**) is a discussion (dispute), which is a public and official debate on scientific topics. Witnesses from both sides will participate in this. It examines the issues in depth. Both sides ask each other questions. The parties defend their point of view and exchange arguments that weaken the opposing side. The goal is to prove the truth by refuting the opponent.

Debate is to clarify the issue through mutual discussion, and in the debate, in addition to the above, it is necessary to deprive the opponent of evidence and to determine the correctness of one's side, to protect it from contradictory evidence.

Scientists have developed 8 rules of debate, including: objective intent; the discussion is based on the Qur'an and the Sunnah; to have knowledge; mutual love and brotherhood; lack of calmness and excitement; accepting the truth immediately when it becomes clear; not to spread the opponent's defeat; They include stopping the discussion if one of the parties stubbornly insists on not accepting the arguments.

Taking into account the given information, the following can be concluded. In Islam, negative attitudes towards several types of debate can be seen. This is "al-mirou" - in most cases, a negative argument is an argument, a fanatical defense of one's opinion without considering the arguments of the opponent. Knowing that one's own is superior and belittling the opponent's. "Al-Jidal" - rarely found in the meaning of "al-mirou", in most cases it is aimed at proving the inconsistency of the opponent's arguments. The opponent is directed to destroy the document as if disarming it. "Al-Ikhtisam" is often a futile discussion, aimed at protecting

¹⁵ Holy Quran: translation and interpretation of meanings / translation and interpretation author: Abdulaziz Mansur. – T: TIU, 2012. – P.225.

¹⁶ Holy Quran: translation and interpretation of meanings / translation and interpretation author: Abdulaziz Mansur. –T: TIU, 2012. – P.281.

¹⁷ That source. – P.542.

¹⁸ That source. – P.519.

the opinions of the opponent, not at proving the inconsistency of his arguments. From this point of view, "al-ikhtisam" is considered a defensive argument.

There are also debates approved by scholars, which can be seen to be based on scientificity, decency and objectivity, such as "al-munozara" and "al-munaqasha". People who are in search of knowledge are recommended by scientists to debate in this direction.

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